

Optimized Control of an Islanded DC Microgrid with Solar, Wind, Battery, and Supercapacitor Systems for Electric Vehicle and AC-DC Load Management

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To Cite this Article

A. Gowthami & Dr. K. Siva Kumar (2025). Optimized Control of an Islanded DC Microgrid with Solar, Wind, Battery, and Supercapacitor Systems for Electric Vehicle and AC-DC Load Management. International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology, 11(06), 191-202. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15715161>

Article Info

Received: 30 May 2025; Accepted: 19 June 2025.; Published: 22 June 2025.

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KEYWORDS

Islanded DC Microgrid,
Electric Vehicle Charging,
Solar, Wind,
Permanent Magnet Synchronous
Generator (PMSG),
Incremental Conductance (INC)
MPPT,
Battery,
Supercapacitor,
DC-DC Converter.

ABSTRACT

This paper presents an advanced power management strategy for an islanded DC microgrid that integrates renewable energy sources such as solar photovoltaic and wind energy along with a hybrid energy storage system consisting of batteries and supercapacitors. The proposed system is designed to efficiently support both AC and DC loads including electric vehicle charging and discharging operations while operating independently from the conventional AC grid. A DC to DC boost converter controlled by an incremental conductance maximum power point tracking algorithm is used to extract optimal power from the wind-driven permanent magnet synchronous generator. A bidirectional DC to DC buck boost converter manages the charging and discharging cycles of the battery and supercapacitor system. The supercapacitor helps reduce voltage and current fluctuations, thereby improving system stability and extending battery lifespan. To ensure reliable and balanced power distribution within the microgrid, a double loop voltage and current control structure is implemented. Additionally, a DC to AC inverter converts the regulated DC link voltage to supply traditional AC loads. This islanded DC microgrid architecture offers a sustainable solution for electric vehicle charging, reduces dependency on fossil fuel-based power infrastructure, and enhances operational resilience during grid outages. The effectiveness of the proposed configuration is validated through simulation results using MATLAB and Simulink under various load and generation conditions.

I. Introduction

The rapid depletion of fossil fuels and the growing concerns over environmental pollution have made the integration of renewable energy sources an essential element in modern power systems [1]. Among the various solutions, the microgrid has emerged as a promising decentralized approach to meet energy demands in a sustainable and efficient manner. Particularly, direct current microgrids are gaining significant attention due to their high efficiency, simpler control mechanisms, and compatibility with a wide range of distributed energy resources and modern DC loads [2]. In islanded operation, where the microgrid operates independently of the utility grid, maintaining stability and power balance becomes both critical and challenging [3]. The increasing penetration of solar photovoltaic and wind energy systems has become a dominant trend in decentralized generation due to their clean, renewable, and inexhaustible nature [4]. However, the inherent intermittency and unpredictability of these renewable sources pose major challenges in maintaining voltage stability, load matching, and power quality in isolated microgrids [5]. Wind energy, particularly when harnessed through permanent magnet synchronous generators, has been widely used in distributed generation because of its high efficiency, compact size, and ability to operate under variable wind speeds [6]. To ensure maximum energy harvesting from such systems, maximum power point tracking techniques are essential. The incremental conductance method is one of the most efficient MPPT algorithms, particularly suited for wind and solar systems where environmental conditions fluctuate rapidly [7][8]. Solar energy systems, often based on photovoltaic arrays, complement wind energy systems by offering generation during daylight hours, thereby increasing overall system reliability and energy availability [9]. However, the mismatch between energy generation and consumption necessitates the inclusion of energy storage systems to buffer surplus energy and deliver it during demand peaks [10]. In this context, hybrid energy storage systems combining batteries and supercapacitors have emerged as a robust solution. Batteries, with their high energy density, provide long-term energy support, while supercapacitors, known for their rapid response and high power density, are suited for smoothing out transient disturbances and

handling instantaneous power demands [11][12]. The synergy between batteries and supercapacitors not only ensures effective power balancing but also significantly improves the operational lifespan of the battery by reducing its exposure to high current and frequent charge-discharge cycles [13]. The use of supercapacitors to offload high-frequency transients and short-duration load peaks from the battery has been proven effective in enhancing system robustness [14]. Managing such hybrid storage systems requires a sophisticated power control strategy that can coordinate energy exchange across the microgrid while ensuring reliability and efficiency [15]. Electric vehicles have introduced a new dimension to load demand in modern power systems. With the increasing adoption of electric vehicles globally, the need for reliable and fast charging infrastructure is expanding [16]. The integration of electric vehicle charging stations into microgrids enables localized energy management and supports clean transportation goals. Moreover, EVs can act as flexible loads or even distributed storage devices, enabling vehicle-to-grid operations when needed [17]. In isolated microgrids, managing the charging and discharging behavior of EVs, while maintaining system stability and energy efficiency, becomes a critical challenge [18]. To manage energy flow effectively in such complex systems, advanced power electronic converters are employed. DC to DC boost converters are used to interface variable DC sources such as wind-driven PMSGs with the DC link. These converters, when coupled with incremental conductance MPPT, enable precise control of energy extraction from the wind resource [19]. For storage management, bidirectional buck boost DC to DC converters are employed to regulate the charging and discharging cycles of both batteries and supercapacitors [20]. The bidirectional nature of these converters allows seamless energy exchange between the storage units and the microgrid, facilitating both supply support and energy absorption during surplus conditions [21]. A double loop control architecture, which includes both voltage and current regulation loops, is essential for maintaining a stable DC link and managing energy sharing across multiple sources and loads [22]. This layered control structure enhances the dynamic response of the system and ensures accurate power distribution even under rapidly

changing load conditions or source availability. Moreover, the conversion of DC to AC using voltage source inverters allows the microgrid to supply conventional AC loads, increasing its applicability in hybrid load environments [23]. Recent research efforts have demonstrated the technical feasibility and benefits of integrating renewable energy with hybrid energy storage systems in microgrids [24]. However, many existing solutions focus on either grid-connected systems or limited combinations of energy sources and storage technologies, often lacking comprehensive strategies for fully islanded operation involving multiple types of loads including electric vehicles. There remains a significant gap in designing control systems that can unify the coordination of renewable generation, hybrid energy storage, and multi-type load management in a resilient and scalable framework [25]. In response to this challenge, this paper proposes a comprehensive control and energy management strategy for an islanded DC microgrid that integrates solar photovoltaic, wind energy via permanent magnet synchronous generators, a hybrid battery and supercapacitor-based storage system, and support for both AC and DC loads. The system employs a DC to DC boost converter with an incremental conductance MPPT algorithm for optimal wind energy harvesting, and a bidirectional buck boost converter for hybrid storage control. A double loop voltage and current controller ensures stable power sharing and load regulation, while a DC to AC inverter supports conventional AC loads. Simulation studies

conducted in MATLAB and Simulink validate the proposed architecture under various operating scenarios, confirming its effectiveness, flexibility, and resilience in real-world microgrid applications.

II. System Configuration

The proposed system is an islanded DC microgrid that integrates solar photovoltaic, wind energy, and a hybrid energy storage system composed of batteries and supercapacitors to supply both AC and DC loads, including electric vehicle charging as shown in Fig.1. The wind energy is harnessed using a permanent magnet synchronous generator whose variable AC output is rectified and fed into a DC-DC boost converter. This converter operates under the control of an incremental conductance MPPT algorithm to extract maximum power from the wind resource. The solar PV array directly supplies DC power to the bus, complementing the wind generation. A bidirectional buck-boost converter manages the hybrid energy storage system. The battery provides long-term energy support while the supercapacitor handles short-term power fluctuations, improving overall system stability and extending battery life. A double-loop voltage and current controller regulates energy flow and maintains the DC link voltage. To support AC loads, a DC-AC inverter converts the regulated DC output into AC power. The system supports EV charging and discharging through direct DC interfacing, offering high efficiency and grid independence in an islanded mode.

Fig.1 Proposed islanded DC Microgrid system

III. DC Microgrid Component Design

A. Modeling and Designing of a Single-Diode Solar Panel

The single-diode model is one of the most commonly used electrical equivalent circuit models to represent the behavior of a solar photovoltaic (PV) cell or panel. It provides a good balance between simplicity and accuracy, capturing the essential characteristics of solar cells under various irradiance and temperature conditions. A photovoltaic (PV) cell converts sunlight directly into electricity through the photovoltaic effect. When sunlight hits the semiconductor material of the PV cell (typically silicon), it excites electrons, generating electron-hole pairs. These charge carriers are separated by the internal electric field of the p-n junction, generating a current if the circuit is closed as shown in Fig.2. The current-voltage (I-V) characteristics of the PV cell are non-linear and are affected by factors like solar irradiance and temperature. The single-diode model represents the PV cell using a current source (representing the photocurrent), a diode (representing the p-n junction), and series and shunt resistances (modeling internal losses).

Fig. 2 equivalent model of PV solar.

The output current I of the solar cell is expressed as:

$$I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left(e^{\frac{V+IR_s}{nV_t}} - 1 \right) - \frac{V+IR_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- I = Output current (A)
- V = Output voltage (V)
- I_{ph} = Photocurrent (light-generated current) (A)
- I_0 = Diode saturation current (A)
- R_s = Series resistance (Ω)
- R_{sh} = Shunt resistance (Ω)
- n = Ideality factor of the diode (typically 1 to 2)
- V_t = Thermal voltage (V), given by:

$$V_t = \frac{kT}{q} \quad (2)$$

Where

k = Boltzmann constant = $1.38 \times 10^{-23} \text{ J/K}$

T = Cell temperature in Kelvin

q = Electron charge = $1.6 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C}$

a. Photocurrent I_{ph}

The photocurrent is a function of irradiance G and temperature T , and can be approximated as:

$$I_{ph} = [I_{sc} + K_i(T - T_{ref})] \cdot \frac{G}{G_{ref}} \quad (3)$$

Where:

- I_{sc} = Short circuit current at reference conditions (A)
- K_i = Temperature coefficient of current ($\text{A}/^\circ\text{C}$)
- T = Cell temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)
- T_{ref} = Reference temperature (usually 25°C)
- G = Solar irradiance (W/m^2)
- G_{ref} = Reference irradiance (usually $1000 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$)

b. Diode Saturation Current I_0

$$I_0 = I_{rs} \left(\frac{T}{T_{ref}} \right)^3 \cdot \exp \left(\frac{qE_g}{nk} \left(\frac{1}{T_{ref}} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right) \quad (4)$$

Where:

- I_{rs} = Reverse saturation current at T_{ref}
- E_g = Band gap energy of the semiconductor (e.g., 1.12 eV for silicon)

B. Solar DC-DC Boost Converter with INC MPPT Controller

A DC-DC boost converter is commonly used in photovoltaic (PV) systems to step up the output voltage of the solar panel to a desired DC bus level. To ensure maximum power extraction from the solar panel under varying irradiance and temperature conditions, the Incremental Conductance (INC) MPPT algorithm is used as a control strategy as shown in Fig.3. The INC algorithm offers better tracking accuracy under rapidly changing conditions compared to the Perturb and Observe (P&O) method. A boost converter steps up the input voltage by storing energy in an inductor and releasing it through a diode to the output. It operates in two modes:

- Mode 1 (Switch ON): The switch (typically a MOSFET or IGBT) is closed. Current flows through the inductor and energy is stored in its magnetic field.

- Mode 2 (Switch OFF): The switch is opened. The inductor releases its stored energy through the diode to the output capacitor and load, increasing the output voltage.

Fig. 3 solar PV INC MPPT DC-DC boost converter

The output voltage of an ideal boost converter is given by:

$$V_0 = \frac{V_{in}}{1-D} \quad (5)$$

Design Considerations for Components

- Inductor (L):

$$L = \frac{V_{in} \cdot D}{\Delta I \cdot f_s} \quad (6)$$

- Output Capacitor (C):

$$C = \frac{I_{out} \cdot D}{f_s \cdot \Delta V_{out}} \quad (7)$$

C. INC MPPT Algorithm – Operating Logic

The Incremental Conductance (INC) method is based on the fact that the derivative of power with respect to voltage is zero at the maximum power point (MPP), positive to the left of MPP, and negative to the right as shown in Fig.4.

$$\frac{dP}{dV} = \frac{d(IV)}{dV} = I + V \frac{dI}{dV} \quad (8)$$

- At MPP: $\frac{dP}{dV} = 0 \Rightarrow \frac{dI}{dV} = -\frac{I}{V}$ (9)

- Left of MPP: $\frac{dI}{dV} > -\frac{I}{V} \Rightarrow \frac{dP}{dV} > 0$ (10)

- Right of MPP: $\frac{dI}{dV} < -\frac{I}{V} \Rightarrow \frac{dP}{dV} < 0$ (11)

Algorithm Steps:

1. Measure $I(k)$ and $V(k)$
2. Compute $\Delta I = I(k) - I(k-1)$, $\Delta V(k) = V(k) - V(k-1)$
3. If $\Delta V = 0$
 - If $\Delta I = 0$: MPP reached \rightarrow No change
 - If $\Delta I > 0$: Left of Mpp \rightarrow Decrease voltage (decrease duty)

- If $\Delta I < 0$: Right of MPP \rightarrow Increase voltage (increase duty)
4. $\Delta V \neq 0$
 - If $\frac{\Delta I}{\Delta V} = -\frac{I}{V}$: MPP
 - If $\frac{\Delta I}{\Delta V} > -\frac{I}{V}$: Left of Mpp \rightarrow Decrease duty
 - If $\frac{\Delta I}{\Delta V} < -\frac{I}{V}$: Right of MPP \rightarrow Increase duty

Fig. 4. Flow chart of INC algorithm of MPPT for solar conversion.

D. Wind Energy Conversion System Using PMSG and INC MPPT Control

A wind energy conversion system (WECS) transforms the kinetic energy of wind into electrical energy. The wind turbine captures wind energy and transmits mechanical power to a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (PMSG), which produces variable-frequency AC power. This is rectified into DC, followed by a DC-DC boost converter controlled via the Incremental Conductance (INC) MPPT algorithm to extract maximum power under varying wind speeds as shown in Fig.5.

Fig. 5 wind energy conversion system with INC MPPT DC-DC boost converter

a. Wind Turbine Power Equation

The mechanical power P_m extracted from wind is:

$$P_m = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot A \cdot V_w^3 \cdot C_p(\lambda, \beta) \quad (12)$$

Where:

- ρ = Air density (kg/m³)
- A = Swept area of blades (m²) = πR^2
- V_w = Wind speed (m/s)
- C_p = Power coefficient (function of tip speed ratio λ and blade pitch angle β)
- λ = Tip speed ratio = $\frac{\omega_t R}{V_w}$
- ω_t = Turbine angular speed (rad/s)

C_p is maximized at a specific λ , which defines the Maximum Power Point (MPP).

b. PMSG Modeling

The PMSG is modeled using the dq-axis equations in the rotor reference frame:

$$V_d = R_s i_d + L_d \frac{di_d}{dt} + \omega_e L_q i_q \quad (13)$$

$$V_q = R_s i_q + L_q \frac{di_q}{dt} + \omega_e L_d i_d + \omega_e \lambda_m \quad (14)$$

Where:

- R_s : Stator resistance
- L_d, L_q : d- and q-axis inductances
- ω_e : Electrical angular speed
- λ_m : Flux linkage due to permanent magnets

In stand-alone or DC microgrid applications, the PMSG's AC output is rectified to DC using a diode bridge or a controlled rectifier.

c. Rectifier and DC-DC Boost Converter

The three-phase diode bridge rectifier converts PMSG's variable-frequency AC output to unregulated DC. To stabilize the DC voltage and track maximum wind power, a DC-DC boost converter is used.

Boost Converter Equation:

$$V_{out} = \frac{V_{in}}{1-D} \quad (15)$$

Where D is the duty cycle.

d. MPPT Using Incremental Conductance (INC)

To operate the turbine-generator system at MPP despite varying wind speeds, the INC MPPT algorithm is applied to the boost converter as shown in Fig.6.

$$\frac{dP}{dV} = I + V \frac{dI}{dV} \quad (16)$$

- If $\frac{dP}{dV} = 0 \Rightarrow$ MPP reached
- If $\frac{dP}{dV} > 0 \Rightarrow$ Increase duty (extract more power)
- If $\frac{dP}{dV} < 0 \Rightarrow$ Decrease duty

In WECS, V and I are measured at the DC output after rectification.

Fig. 6. Flow chart of INC algorithm of MPPT for wind conversion.

E. Modeling and Designing of a Bidirectional Buck-Boost Converter

1. Introduction and System Overview

The combined strengths of lithium-ion batteries and supercapacitors allow for hybrid energy storage devices, which take use of both technologies' high power densities and energy densities as shown in Fig.7. The DC bus and these storage parts may be effectively managed with the help of a bidirectional buck-boost converter. Power may be transported in either way, from charging storage devices to powering the load, thanks to its ability to perform both step-down (buck) and step-up (boost) operations. When the battery is being charged or discharged, or when the supercapacitor is handling high-power transients, this converter must control the voltage effectively.

2. Operating Modes

The converter operates in two primary modes:

Fig.7 circuit diagram of DC-DC bidirectional buck boost converter

- **Buck Mode (Step-Down):** When the voltage on the DC bus is lower than the battery voltage (or supercapacitor voltage), the converter operates in buck mode to step down the voltage. This is typically used when discharging energy from the storage system to the bus or load.
- **Boost Mode (Step-Up):** When the voltage on the DC bus is higher than the storage voltage, the converter operates in boost mode to step up the voltage. This mode is used when charging the storage elements from the DC bus.

A single converter can operate in either mode by adjusting the duty cycle of its switching devices. In bidirectional operation, the power electronics (usually using MOSFETs or IGBTs) are arranged in an H-bridge or similar topology to allow current flow in both directions.

$$V_{out} = D \cdot V_{in} \quad (17)$$

Where: V_{in} is the input voltage (from the battery or DC bus), V_{out} is the regulated output voltage (to the load or storage device), D is the duty cycle, with $0 < D < 1$.

3. Boost Mode (Step-Up Operation)

In boost mode, the converter increases the input voltage to a higher output voltage. The output voltage is expressed as:

$$V_{out} = \frac{V_{in}}{1-D} \quad (18)$$

Where: V_{in} is the lower voltage from the storage device or DC bus, V_{out} is the higher regulated voltage, D is the duty cycle, with $0 < D < 1$.

4. Inductor and Capacitor Design

For both modes, an inductor L and output capacitor C are essential for smoothing the current and voltage ripples.

4.1 Inductor Design

To ensure continuous conduction mode (CCM) and limit the inductor current ripple (ΔI_L), the inductor value can be estimated by:

$$L = \frac{(V_{in} - V_{out}) \cdot D}{f_s \cdot \Delta I_L} \quad (\text{Buck Mode}) \quad (19)$$

$$L = \frac{V_{in} \cdot D}{f_s \cdot \Delta I_L} \quad (\text{Boost Mode}) \quad (20)$$

Where: f_s is the switching frequency, ΔI_L is the desired peak-to-peak inductor current ripple.

4.2. Capacitor Design

The output capacitor C smooths the voltage ripple (ΔV_{out}) at the output and is given by:

$$C = \frac{I_{out} \cdot D}{f_s \cdot \Delta V_{out}} \quad (21)$$

Where: I_{out} is the load or charging current, ΔV_{out} is the acceptable output voltage ripple.

F. Modeling and Designing of Lithium-Ion Battery and Supercapacitor.

In modern power systems, Hybrid Energy Storage Systems (HESS) integrates two or more energy storage devices to optimize power and energy performance. Lithium-ion batteries offer high energy density, making them ideal for sustained energy supply. Supercapacitors (SCs) offer high power density and rapid charge/discharge capabilities, making them ideal for handling transient loads or power fluctuations. Combining both enables better load balancing, longer battery life, and faster response times, especially in applications like EV charging, renewable integration, and microgrids as shown in Fig.8 and 9.

A. Lithium-Ion Battery Modeling

Lithium-ion batteries are typically modeled using electrical equivalent circuits, such as the Thevenin model or Rint (resistance-in-series) model, which account for the terminal voltage, internal resistance, and state of charge (SOC).

Fig.8 bidirectional dc-dc buck boost converter BESS

a. Rint Model

The simplest model is:

$$V_{bat} = V_{oc}(SOC) - I_{bat} \cdot R_{int} \quad (22)$$

Where: Vbat: terminal voltage of the battery (V), VOC (SOC): open circuit voltage as a function of state of charge, Ibat: battery current (positive for discharge, negative for charge), Rint: internal resistance of the battery (Ω)

b. State of Charge (SOC)

SOC represents the available capacity and is updated as:

$$soc(t) = soc(t_0) - \frac{1}{C_{bat}} \int_{t_0}^t I_{bat}(t) dt \quad (23)$$

Where:

- SOC(t0): initial SOC
- Cbat: nominal capacity of the battery in Ah
- Ibat(t): battery current at time t

c. Energy Stored

$$E_{bat} = C_{bat} \cdot V_{nom} \quad (24)$$

B. Supercapacitor Modeling

Supercapacitors are modeled as ideal capacitors in series with a small equivalent series resistance (ESR).

Fig.9 Super capacitor banks

$$V_{sc}(t) = \frac{1}{C_{sc}} \int_{t_0}^t I_{sc}(t) dt + I_{sc}(t) \cdot R_{sc} \quad (25)$$

Where: VSC(t): terminal voltage of the supercapacitor, CSC: capacitance in Farads, ISC(t): current through the supercapacitor, RSC: equivalent series resistance (Ω)

Equation of Energy Stored for supercapacitor

$$E_{sc} = \frac{1}{2} C_{sc} V_{sc}^2 \quad (26)$$

Fig. 10 Proposed energy management strategy for the BESS

Fig. 11 Proposed energy management strategy for the Supercapacitor

VI. Inverter operation for AC load

In a DC grid-based renewable energy system, the inverter serves as a vital interface for supplying AC loads. After generating electrical energy from sources such as solar photovoltaic (PV) panels and wind turbines, and conditioning it through rectifiers, MPPT controllers, and buck converters, the resulting DC power is made available on a common DC bus. To power conventional AC appliances or feed the utility grid, this DC power must be converted back into AC, which is achieved using a Voltage Source Inverter (VSI). The VSI employs semiconductor switches, typically IGBTs or MOSFETs, arranged in either single-phase or three-phase full-bridge configurations as shown in Fig.12. The switching operation is controlled through Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) techniques, most commonly Sinusoidal PWM (SPWM), to generate an AC voltage waveform that closely resembles a sinusoidal signal. This process involves switching the DC voltage on and off at high frequencies and modulating the duty cycle to control the amplitude and frequency of the output voltage. The resulting waveform contains high-frequency harmonics, which are then filtered out using an LC low-pass filter to produce a clean AC output suitable for household or industrial loads. Thus, the

inverter enables seamless integration of renewable DC power into AC applications while maintaining voltage stability, frequency accuracy, and load compatibility.

Fig.12 inverter Conversion design for AC load

Fig.13 Inverter controller

V. EV-Based Backup Power Support for AC and DC Applications

In the islanded DC microgrid system, the electric vehicle (EV) battery is not only charged from the microgrid but also serves as a power source for AC and DC loads during discharge conditions. This is made possible through a DC-DC bidirectional buck-boost converter, which allows energy to flow from the EV battery back into the DC bus as shown in Fig.14. When supplying DC loads, the converter boosts the EV battery voltage to maintain the required DC link level. For AC loads, the boosted voltage is further processed by a DC-AC inverter, which converts the regulated DC power into AC form suitable for household appliances and other AC equipment. This configuration enables the EV to act as a backup energy source, especially during periods of low renewable generation or unexpected load demand. The bidirectional converter ensures efficient and controlled power flow, while the double-loop controller maintains voltage stability and prevents battery over-discharge, thereby making the EV a reliable support element for powering both AC and DC loads in the standalone microgrid.

Fig.14 bidirectional DC-DC buck-boost converter for EV charging system

VI. Simulation results and Discussion

The proposed islanded DC microgrid was simulated using MATLAB Simulink for a total duration of 1 second to evaluate its performance under varying environmental and load conditions. The system integrates a 12 kilowatt solar photovoltaic array, a 7.5 kilowatt wind energy generation unit, a 20 kilowatt battery energy storage system, and a supercapacitor for handling transient responses. The DC link voltage was maintained at 400 volts, and a DC to AC inverter converted this voltage to supply traditional AC loads at 230 volts. The system also powered a 6.5 kilowatt DC load and supported electric vehicle charging for a battery rated at 14.5 kilowatt capacity. From 0 to 0.2 seconds, the solar irradiance was constant at 1000 watts per square meter, enabling the solar PV system to operate at its full capacity of 12 kilowatts. After 0.2 seconds, the irradiance began decreasing linearly, reaching 500 watts per square meter by 1 second, which led to a corresponding reduction in solar power output. Simultaneously, the wind speed was held at 12 meters per second until 0.4 seconds, during which the wind generator delivered its rated power of 7.5 kilowatts. From 0.4 to 1 second, the wind speed decreased gradually to 6 meters per second, reducing wind power generation significantly. During these fluctuations in renewable power generation, the 20 kilowatt battery system and the supercapacitor played a crucial role in maintaining power balance. The battery provided steady power to the loads, while the supercapacitor mitigated voltage and current fluctuations by responding rapidly to transient changes. As a result, the 6.5 kilowatt DC load was supplied without interruption throughout the simulation period. The hybrid energy storage combination effectively absorbed the mismatch between generation and load, ensuring that system stability was preserved. Electric vehicle charging commenced at 0.6

seconds, starting at a power level of 7.25 kilowatts. From 0.8 seconds to 1 second, the charging power increased to the full rated value of 14.5 kilowatts. Despite the concurrent power demand from AC loads, DC loads, and the EV battery, the microgrid maintained a well-regulated DC link voltage of 400 volts, with deviations limited to within ± 1.5 percent. The AC inverter delivered a constant output of 230 volts RMS with a Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) of less than 2 percent, ensuring compatibility with sensitive AC equipment. Overall, the simulation results validate that the proposed islanded DC microgrid is capable of managing dynamic changes in renewable generation and load conditions as shown in Fig.15. The system maintained reliable operation, ensured continuous supply to both AC and DC loads, and successfully performed electric vehicle charging in an isolated mode without relying on the main grid. This demonstrates the effectiveness of the integrated control strategy and the coordination between renewable sources and hybrid energy storage systems.

Fig.15 Simulation Results of Islanded DC Microgrid under Dynamic Generation and Load Conditions

VII. Conclusion

This work presents an optimized control strategy for an islanded DC microgrid that integrates renewable energy sources such as solar and wind with a hybrid energy storage system consisting of a battery and a supercapacitor. The proposed system is designed to supply both AC and DC loads reliably, including the dynamic charging needs of electric vehicles, under fluctuating environmental and load conditions. The use of an incremental conductance-based MPPT algorithm

for the wind-driven permanent magnet synchronous generator and a bidirectional buck-boost converter for energy storage management ensures efficient power extraction and delivery. Simulation results obtained through MATLAB and Simulink confirm that the microgrid maintains stable DC link voltage and AC output voltage, even under variable solar irradiance, changing wind speeds, and time-varying EV charging loads. The supercapacitor effectively mitigates voltage and current transients, thereby improving overall system stability and protecting the battery from stress. The coordinated operation of the power converters and control loops guarantees uninterrupted power supply to critical AC and DC loads, even in the absence of grid support. Overall, the proposed islanded DC microgrid architecture demonstrates a highly resilient, energy-efficient, and sustainable solution for remote or standalone energy systems. It enables reliable EV charging while simultaneously reducing dependency on fossil fuels and enhancing the operational flexibility of renewable-rich power networks.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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